

A NOTE ON THE APPLICATION OF THE BOWMAN AND SCOTT METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF NITROGEN IN GUNCOTTON

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The nitrogen content of guncotton is usually determined by the nitrometer. The reported errors of the method are due to (i) the solubility of NO in H₂SO₄ and (ii) the simultaneous formation of other gases from the degradation of the cellulose molecule (Beckett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 117, 220; Hill, *Analyst*, 1918, 48, 215).

Other methods have been proposed alternative to the nitrometer method. Among these the one evolved by Bowman and Scott (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1915, 7, 766) for the estimation of small quantities of HNO₃ in oleum, has been adapted by Mange (*L. Ind. Chim.*, 1918, 5, 255) for the estimation of nitrogen in guncotton; the method does not, however, appear to have been used in the routine analysis of guncotton. According to Bowman and Scott the reaction is

When HNO₃ has all reacted, N₂O₃ is reduced by excess of FeSO₄ to $\bar{\text{N}}\text{O}$; the end-point is the formation of the pinkish brown complex, FeSO₄—NO.

It was found that, following the details as given in Worden, ("Technology of Cellulose Esters," Vol. I, Part II, p. 978) reproducible results could not be obtained with guncotton. The following modifications were therefore found necessary.

(i) Ferrous ammonium sulphate (240 g. per litre in 60% H₂SO₄) was standardised against KNO₃, instead of against K₂Cr₂O₇; this obviated the correction in the titre suggested in the original method. (ii) Titration was effected at about 5°. (iii) In view of the high concentration of ferrous ammonium sulphate used (*vide infra*) titration was carried out in a burette reading to 0.05 ml.

The results obtained are detailed in Tables I and II.

Procedure

A known weight (about 0.5g.) of dried guncotton was introduced into a 250 ml. Erlenmeyer flask, 70 ml. conc. H₂SO₄ added and stoppered. The dissolution is effected with constant shaking at about 15°. After the guncotton has all dissolved, the flask is closed with a bored rubber-stopper and is placed in an ice-bath (a wide beaker is convenient). The standard titre is run in very slowly through a fine jet attached to the burette, the jet being well below the surface of the acid. The flask is shaken well throughout the titration. Towards the end, the titration is effected dropwise, until a permanent pink colour is obtained. The estimation takes about half an hour. Following points should be carefully noted in this connection:

(i) The mixing of the titre with the contents of the flask must be thorough and intimate; else, due to local concentration of ferrous sulphate, the FeSO₄—NO complex is precipitated, vitiating the result. Further, this pink-coloured precipitate obscures the end-point and cannot be redissolved unless by warming to room temperature. (ii) When within 1 ml. of the end-point, as determined in a preliminary run, the flask is to be taken out of the ice-jacket, and titration completed. While perfect cooling and very slow addition of titre are necessary in the early stages, to avoid (a) local heating leading to loss of HNO₃ and (b) formation of FeSO₄—NO complex with its disadvantages mentioned above, these precautions need not be strictly adhered to towards the end. (iii) For standardisation of ferrous ammonium

sulphate, about 0.5 g. of KNO_3 is a convenient quantity to work with. To obtain accurate results, about 0.5 g. of guncotton is taken for each test ; this weight contains nitrogen almost equivalent to that contained in the primary standard.

Besides estimating nitric acid, nitrates and guncotton, the method seems capable of estimating in general, all organic nitric esters, which yield nitric acid on dissolution in conc. H_2SO_4 .

TABLE I

N content of a composite sample of guncotton as determined by

FeAm. Sulphate.	Nitrometer.
13'08	13'01
13'09	13'03
13'09	13'01
13'10	12'97
13'12	13'04
13'02	12'98
13'07	13'01
13'11	12'99
13'09	13'00
13'11	13'02
13'09	13'02
13'04	13'04

TABLE II

N content of different samples of guncotton as determined by

FeAm. Sulphate.	Nitrometer.
12'88, 0'87	12'97, 0'97
13'19, 0'22	13'02, 0'00
13'03, 0'02	13'01, 0'00
13'03, 0'00	12'98, 0'96
12'98, 0'99	12'88, 0'88
12'91, 0'93	12'90, 0'89
13'03, 0'05	13'06, 0'04
13'16, 0'14	13'01, 0'00
13'04, 0'08	13'02, 0'04
13'08, 0'10	13'07, 0'09
12'96, 0'95	12'95 —
13'20, 0'17	13'11, 0'09

The authors are indebted to Dr. H. R. Ambler, Ph.D., F.R.I.C., Chief Inspector of Military Explosives, for his kind interest in the work and to the Director of Armaments for kind permission to publish it.

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Received November 20, 1944.